

Let select a Business School: Factors that Affect Student's Selection of a Business School

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Abstract

In a student's life the choice of the institution which he or she is going to attend after F.sc/ A. levels is of critical nature. A lot of factors influence this choice made by the students, these may include perceptions of universities, colleges and student life therein, which students generally develop early on in their life. Every student wants to enroll in a university of good ranking and popularity, which can help his/her attain his/her, future goals. The study in hand illustrates the factors that attract students in the business department of different universities.

Introduction

The selection of an institution to obtain a degree is a matter of serious concern in student's life. In this regard, the preference of student towards a specific institution is ingredient by various factors. In this backdrop, this study addresses and highlights the factors affecting the student's choice to join a business school. To test the hypothesis of this study, results are drawn from primary data which explored the factors impacting the student's choice to get enrolled in business school in Islamabad e.g. location of campus, fee structure, qualification of faculty. The institutions that are taken as a case study are;

It is interesting to find that this study illustrates that there are almost no relevance between qualification of faculty and number of student in that institution; same is the case with fee structure and student's choice. Whereas the ranking of institution by the Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan, location of the campus, peer pressure, and student's parents views about the institution influence the student's decision in choosing a specific institution.

Being exploratory in nature, this study has dwell upon the important aspect of educational arena, and hence provides the rational way forward to address the challenges.

Purpose of the study

The motivation behind this study is to learn and to investigate with respect to how Pakistani school students which are trying to attempt higher education base their decision. An attempt has been made to investigate what factors influence a student's choice of university and why students ponder one special degree or specific program at a university.

This study is especially helpful for advanced education administration, as increased knowledge will prompt them to better making arrangements for future generations of students. While this research will be most beneficial for Pakistan, other countries' educational systems may also benefit from the same. Finally, the discoveries will essentially manage advanced education foundations in their planning and strategy making.

Significance of the study

The importance of the study is to highlight what factors influence students in making their choice about higher education institution amongst Pakistani universities. While helping the institutes and academia get a better understanding of students' choices and their decision making patterns, on a greater scale, the Government of Pakistan, the Ministry of Education specifically, can also utilize the results of this research to comprehend the decision making process of high school students concerning their institution choice, so that better instructive arrangements and better academic advising frameworks may be put into place.

Guardians of students and students themselves will also benefit from this research – they may take a look into factors affecting other students and make more informed and better choices. What's more, advanced education establishments could likewise arrange their hiring and affirmation strategies and frameworks to

better describe the requirements of their potential customers. Concerning the social phase of this research, the common population as a rule for understanding more precisely will have all the important information about the higher education for upcoming eras.

The study will be particularly critical in light of the fact that the data on inclinations of higher education institutions and courses will be better comprehended with regards to Pakistani culture and other similar cultures.

Problem Statement

It is the common phenomenon that how students select the particular business school especially in developing countries like Pakistan and it's all due to the different factors which may include:

- Wrong place selection
- Choice of wrong Business School
- Student takes loan to take admission in any business school

So, these are few those factors which are highly responsible for the wrong selection of the business school that normally students do because they normally face all those factors in country like Pakistan .So, our research purpose is to identify all those factors which are problematic and then to identify those factors which students consider when they are making any decision to take admission in any business school.

Objective of the Study

Thus, the objective of the study is to analyses, evaluate and explore the factors effecting the student's decision to choose the specific campus.

Research Questions

This study will seek the answers of following questions:

- What factors affect student's selection of Business schools in Pakistan?
- How have economic opportunities affected student's choice to join/get enrolled in Business school?
- Why students choose to join business school in Pakistan?

Literature Review

While going through the related literature on the subject at hand, it was revealed that it consisted upon perceptive and affecting results. Subsequently, it was obvious to provide a chronological while undertaking a thorough review on the subject with the purpose to provide the reader deeper knowledge on ways in which factors have remained constant or changed over time. Pakistan was the area where most of the research was conducted and it was found really informative and well based upon the data collection instruments of the study.

Introduction

For students, it is a paradoxical choice to get enrolled in a higher institution e.g. university. It is difficult because there are a lot of contributing factors in making such choice. These contributing factors includes the ontological position of parents and other family members towards university, besides; environment of university, capability and credibility of its faculty, the general opinion of masses about that particular institution and university official. They play a vital role in perception building of university for the student (who is in process to make a choice to get enrolled).

Administration of university plays an important role to any student in making choice a business school in a manner that it can whether agree students to get enroll or not. Every business school, academic information provides a direction to choice best university for higher education purpose. Academic information includes cost like fee structure, education quality, location of university and what image in students mind. Educational institute choice is most important factor of student's life because student's future depend on the education and could have long term effects, e.g. future choices companionships, life partner, location and future life fulfillment. However most of time involves our personal and financial purposes (Kotler& Fox, 1995). Students making choices for their higher education when they decided their future lives and professional what influencing on the business schools (James, Baldwin, & McInnis, 1999)

It's very important too many people provide options to convey their personal idea, opinion, value in life choice of business school. Different researcher formulated the importance of idea and gathering data form high school students what factors affects choice of business school (Smyth, 2012). Student's evaluation and

then decision to go for specific institute can neither be ignore nor underestimated, because it is he who will be having a journey in his/her selected business school.

Benefits of Business school education

In the contemporary era parents are more concerned about the educational achievements of their children. Besides parents, educational policy makers also accentuate upon the aspect that children must have getting the higher education in better quality as well as in well reputed institute. University degree is considered to be the most important guarantee for the personal and economic achievement in a person's life. In the past, many studies indicate that increase in pay, personality at work, better future work options and contentment of life depend on the higher education, because selection of business school or any university plays an important role of student future life (Bowen, 1977). Leslie & Brinkman (1988) Business school surety got more money as compared to high school graduates students. Moreover, business school graduates are permanently employed of their working life, and they are happier and lead self -achieved life (Bowen, 1977).

In this regard, there is another aspect which is considered as the most important, it is a general assumption made by the economists, and country which provides better education system return a good citizen, good person and better contribution of country progress (McGregor, 1994; Wellman, 1999). In result of best business school graduate benefits of Pakistan and open new business less employment rate. In the modern world, business school have more and more competitive, have higher productivity, and increase profit of government on the whole prove enjoyment of life at basic level. Bowen (1977) and Pascarella & Terenzini (1991) proposed that graduates of school are constitutionally, companionably and practically dynamic and liable for, and provide a direction through modern technology for their society and family. Universities emphases to provide a good citizens of society through our education system, they are ready to assume all responsibilities as a citizen. Choosing the business school is important factor of young people they fulfill these needs to understand.

Choice theory

Choice theory developed by Glasser (1998) suggests that although it is general view that all human beings have similar sort of need of life but when it comes to making a choice regarding a particular thing then their behavior vary person to person up to the level of their satisfaction. In the past good or bad is different with each other life encounters, after studying these features we know how to fulfill student's needs. Many different experience we choose different ideas and various learning to satisfy the student's needs.

So many theories explain the choice and behavior, human behavior play an important role by Crossman (2010). According to economic theories, we measure how allocation, production, and utilization of goods and services, these theories emphasize money is important in decision making process. Social exchange theory suggests that does not only money cost and reward matter in decision making process. According to West & Turner (2007) cost is negative value of person and reward is positive value such as acceptance, support and friendship.

Importance of business school choice

Choice of business school is most importance factor of any student's life because education effect on the future life like job etc. At the time of admission students check the academic institutions, their market value, enrollment rate, HEC ranking all things effect on the student's choice of business school for choose best business school. According to research accentuates upon the factor effecting students in making decision to choose a business schools, it also dwell upon the factors which were effecting student's choice in the past. Students preference change time to time according to the change in public policy e.g. enrollment strategies, marketing practices for business school, including family, friends effects the behavior choice of university.

Study undertaken in Pakistan contexts

This study suggests that Pakistani students consider five important elements while making choices of business school selection like choice of university, city, academic programs and family could also effect on the choice of university due to some important reasons: financial support, family expectation, and competition among the family members. Family financial support is most strong factor as compared to other factors because may be well reputed business school fee structure are high amount and family cannot afford the expense like IBA, LUMS etc. every person does not afford that type of business school. Location is also important factor may be university is well managing, well reputed but far from you.

Studied the Pakistani students need and attitude for the business school study, an individual factors and demand of Pakistani students studying the various business school program included gender, age, CGPA, income, occupation, education level of parents. In addition, these factors have positive effects of Pakistani student's intention and demand of business school image and location of university and fee structure of universities. Vocational education is another type of study conducted identifies factors which influence the choice of students in pursuance of vocational education. It included potential employment, tuition fees, personal attitude, curriculum and campus location, usually genesis and intermediate school teachers are put forward in consideration in student's decision to recruit in professional institution.

Student's choice the business school affecting many type of uncertain factors like number of years, gender specification, average of grades, qualification of parents, post, and income of blood relations these characteristics influence on the decision of higher education. Above all studies show female students get more higher education as compared to male students. Parents are highly influence students decision of selecting the university, motivation, expectations. Good financial background students continue studies as compared to inferior background students.

The Future carrier of students has become very popular due to the changing trend of business studies. Accordingly, an issue for both students and parents who has increased academies which are to be selected for the business management education has always been at hand. Examining different reasons which play role in selection of student for business school was done through this research. Result obtained through this research escorts business management students about status and excellence of different academia and also accommodates the school in pinpointing causes which are crucial for the pupil. (Hassan Raza&Muhammad Faheem, may 2014)

The experiment was done here in this analysis to determine motivation of students and factors behind registering in an MBA program proposed by universities in Pakistan .the program is also used to pick and hunt specifications. To get these goals, details were gathered with the help of a thoroughly made and methodized questionnaire and pre-testing was done to check the capability of the equipment. Factors for choosing MBA program by pupil are to fill their personal commitments and enhance their understanding and experience. Also, the students used alumni and visit at the school place as main cause of illumination succeeded by friends' suggestions and university websites. Interpreting the he MBA programs, the students indicated certification from abroad as the most used specifications succeeded by departmental popularity, prestige of the university and admission specifications. (FarhanMehboob, Syed Mir Muhammad Shah &NiazA Bhutto, sept 2012).

The main cause was that these colleges did not reconstruct development in effectiveness of the market or the way MBA applicants have been choosing B Schools in the past few years. B Schools are just focusing on filling up their seats through advertisements and lucrative offers like free laptops, foreign tour and many more. But they miss out on the basic things that the students are now a days looking for while taking admissions in any B school i.e. the placement records with the average and highest salary packages, standard of the companies participating in the placement session. (S. NazneenWaseem&TayyabaZarif, 2012)

Fee structure of some of the B Schools are a bit on the higher end and parents are even managing the same either through their savings or through educational loans for the bright future of their wards But in return of that the students and the parents are concerned about the ROI on the money they are investing. The students wants to get placed with well know reputed brands and that too with a decent salary package. This is the area where the B schools are failing in establishing themselves especially after the year 2008. Good brands with good packages mostly fill up their slots through top B Schools and the smaller ones are neglected. That the reason most of the students now a days prefer to go abroad for B school courses considering that they will get at least an International exposure while studying which will increase their chances of placements after completing the studies 12th. Also the currency factor comes into picture where the earnings will be more as compared to Pakistan. (SochipanChantasuwanno&SineenatSuasungnern 2011).

The graduate school especially Business Management education in Pakistan, a distinct atmosphere is increasing clash among B-Schools to attract the students. Various competitive strategies have been used to attract the students. The study is aimed to identify the various sources of information that influences a student's selection of a B-School in Pakistan. (SushilChhillar, august 2012).

Above mentioned literature provide a meaningful insight towards students choice regarding and particular academic institute. While applying the containers of review it is revealed that then are certain areas of

agreement as well as disagreement. They include the role of some elements which become contributing factor in students decision making process in choosing the academic institution e.g. location of campus, university administration, parents and peer pressure, HEC ranking and fee structure etc.

Gap of study

As the aim of this study is to ease the choice of students to choose the business school, this subject was not addressed/ highlighted in previous studies. So in order to fill the gaps in existing literature, this will address the questions that analyze, evaluate and explore the factors effecting the student's decision to choose the specific campus. Hence, the study is going to be the valuable addition in existing literature.

Methodology

To draw the results of the study quantitate method has been applied and spss is utilize to draw the results.

Research Design

The research design used for this paper is based on case study followed by descriptive, analytical, exploratory, and qualitative. Pakistani total population is almost 20, 00,000,000 and 60% graduations students; it's very huge market of education sector. The study comes under qualitative and descriptive research because the data will be interpreted through SPSS reach conclusion.

The validity and reliability of data was carried out to ensure the pilot test for gathering instrument and questionnaire. The population score of this study is based on top business school of Islamabad like szabist, bahria, nust and fast etc. We distributed the questioner among the business students and 550 questioners are returned out of 700.

The most feasible way in getting the sample size of over 550 designs was chosen for Islamabad business school students, who were about to finalize on the location and which university to go for their education programs and institutions. The investigation was done for assuming data,content-based analysis was employed for the qualitative data,dascriptive data and inferential data.

Data collection process

In this study used qualitative and quantatitive method techniques for data collection, these techniques use in different stages but with same purpose. This research start with qualitative method. Qualitative method is initial strategy to data collection and analysis and then go to quantatitive method. We visted 5-6 times different universities for data of student enrolment, but we where not entertained they refused to provide us enrolment data becasuse of security issues. Then we visited HEC approx. 5-6 times and they finally provide us enrolment data of different universities.

Analysis and result

This research paper of methodology use in both qualitive and quantatitive method, after using mixed method researcher try to answer the research questions through relevant information.

In the light of interpretation, finding and above description were made on the factor affecting choices of pakistani students select the business school for higher education. Some influencing factors in this study are :

- Age
- Gender
- House hold income
- Parents education
- Academic performance

Utilizing a study instrument created by technique, data was assembled as to factors influencing Business school qualities. Influencing factors include:

- Type of university
- Fee structure
- Location of university
- Environment of university
- Admission process
- University ranking

Choice factors

<i>Choice factors</i>	<i>Male</i>			<i>Female</i>		
	Not important %	Most important %	Important %	Not important %	Most important %	Important %
Business schools are a private institution?	15	36	49.9	15	33	51
Business schools are a public institution?	24	41	35	25	50	25
Business schools are affiliated to a religious organization?	21	38	40	24	42	34
Business schools are affiliated with some reputed national or international institutions?	33	41	26	32	44	24
Business schools give admission on the basis of GAT?	36	41	23	33	46	22
Business schools employ modern/latest techniques to teach?	35	42	23	33	44	22
Business schools offer English programs?	16	39	45	13	42	45
The business school is extensive, offering an assortment of scholastic projects in business instruction?	16	36	48	12	38	50
There is remote employees, making the business schools a really global establishment?	18	32	50	16	39	46
Business schools offer different extracurricular exercises on normal premise?	14	34	52	17	36	48
Business schools have its own particular confirmation examination and choice techniques?	18	48	34	20	36	44

Choice factors	Not important %	Most important %	Important %	Not important %	Most important %	Important %
Business schools admission system is highly competitive?	28	40	32	28	39	33
Business schools have a decent notoriety for scholarly magnificence?	35	42	23	33	44	23
Business schools have a decent notoriety for qualified speakers/educators?	16	39	45	13	42	45
Business schools provides liberal environment?	16	36	48	12	38	50
Business schools have well managed transport system?	14	36	50	17	34	49
Business schools have a proper dress code?	22	41	37	22	36	42
Business schools helps in developing strong communication/interpersonal skills?	22	39	39	15	46	39
Employers value the business schools degree?	36	44	20	32	43	25
The Business schools have a decent notoriety for Quality graduates?	28	38	34	29	41	30
Business schools have a decent notoriety for high innovation in all its foundation and showing and learning offices?	35	43	22	33	43	24
Business schools offer satisfactory and quality library assets and administrations?	45	46	9	40	50	10
Business schools are in a convenient location?	29	52	19	32	51	17
Business schools are not far from your residence?	29	55	16	27	54	19
There are understudy quarters and lofts close to the Business schools?	16	68	16	21	67	12
The everyday costs (sustenance, transport, settlement and so on.) on grounds are sensible?	16	67	17	19	68	13
Fee structure is low compared to other Business schools of the same type?	28	61	11	28	59	13
There are conceivable outcomes to apply for a grant?	31	59	10	32	57	
It is conceivable to apply for an advance for convenience costs?	30	59	11	32	58	10

It is conceivable to land low maintenance position on grounds?	32	59	9	30	57	13
It is conceivable to apply for an advance for educational cost?	31	59	10	30	58	12
It is conceivable to join a trade program or concentrate abroad?	32	57	12	35	58	8
Business schools have the academic advising system?	32	59	9	31	58	12
Business schools give vocation direction and employment situation guiding?	31	59	10	29	61	10

Opinion and perception of male and female students influence on the choice of business school, what type of business school more attract the students either public or private. Public business school is important 35% for male and 25% of female students. University affiliated by HEC is another most important factor influence on the choice of business school, because so many university offer different programmes after two or three years of education, students find out that university is not recognize by HEC like Mohi-u-din university in Mirpur.

Many business schools conduct dual admission test, GAT as well as university admission test like air university, most of students were not select that particular business school because of dual test (GAT and university test). Universities own selection process is enough for the selection of business students. A lot of business schools depend on the faculty of business department either they have PhD faculty or not and lecturer deliver their lectures in formal language or not. Universities offer different academic programmes according to the students choice and industry requirements. .

Business school choice influences the universities environment like various extracurricular activities, university dress code, learning environment, computer labs, library etc. For female students, university environment matters a lot as compared to male students. Reputation of the university is important factor for selecting the business schools because many students prefer MBA, MS, M.phil and choose a good reputational business institution for their higher studies. Good reputation means excellent academic, technology, teaching method and qualified lecturer etc. Service providing also has influence on the selection of business school like library, career fair events, study exchange programmes etc.

Location of the university is also more important factor which has influence on choice of business school because students choose own convenient not far from home, hostel, flat etc. University far from their house cause extra transport expense that is not feasible for students. In Researchers perception, when tuition fee is low than the students enrollment rate must high but according to study results tuition fee does not matters, because many business schools have high fee structure and students enrollment rate is also high.

On the other hand some business schools tuition fee is low but students enrollment rate is also low e.g. Hamdard university (Islamabad campus) has low fee structure as compared to other business schools but students enrollment is also very low. Because only tuition fee does not matter another factors have more influence on students choice of business school like campus, HEC ranking, etc. Scholarship offers by the university is also important factor that has influence on students choice of business school because many students did not afford the fee of university and apply for scholarship.

Decision factors

<i>Decision Factor</i>	<i>Male</i>			<i>Female</i>		
	Not important %	Most important %	Important %	Not important %	Most important %	Important %
You consult with your parents	12	41	47	18	32	50
You consult with your teachers	15	33	51	18	36	46
You consult with your school counsellors	14	35	51	17	34	49
You consult with your family relatives	20	38	41	26	33	41
You consult with your friends	20	43	37	25	34	41
You acquire material from the Business schools counsellors before choosing the B-schools.	26	42	32	24	50	27
You get the agreement from your parent before selecting the business schools.	24	35	41	21	46	33
You listen to the advice of friends before choosing the business schools.	33	40	27	32	45	24
You search the information from different sources before selecting the business schools.	33	46	21	35	42	23
You seek guidance from already business school students about enrolment, programs etc.	14	39	47	16	41	43
You get suggestion and guidance passed out students.	13	34	53	15	40	45
You obtain data through media and website about business schools.	17	35	47	17	34	49
You participate in the counselling Different activities arranged in business schools.	20	44	37	25	34	41
You visit the Business schools before choosing the any business schools.	26	42	32	24	49	27
You attend education activities to learn more before choosing the business schools.	24	35	41	21	46	33

According to the above data and study, female students consult more with their parents before choosing any business school/university as compared to male students. Mostly after F.SC/I.CS students consult more with their parents, teachers, family members etc after graduation students get the information through websites, friends, media, newspaper etc. According to this study, results show that parents play an important role in choice of business schools shown in above table 50% importance decision of selecting business school for female students and 47% are male students consult with their parents.

Choice of any business school or higher education university is most important factor and students did not take correct decision without any consultation.

Discussion

The aim of this study was to address the problem of students when they are selecting a particular business school and to identify the factors which are affecting their choice. So in order to fill the gaps in existing literature, this to pick will address the Questions that analyses, evaluate and explore the factors effecting the student's decision to choose the specific campus. Hence, the study in hand is going to be the valuable addition in existing literature. With the help of this study in future, students can easily choose the business schools and more specifically check their study compatibilities with that institution. This study contributes to develop quality education in business school and helps them to attract students. Because this is first study which is conducted in details to find out the factors which affects the choice of students and their mentality for taking admission in a particular business school.

Limitation

- Due to shortage of time span and lack of resources this study did not cover the each and every aspect of student's choice so it is confined to merely location of university, HEC ranking, qualification of faculty, and fee structure etc.
- Factor analysis could determine various demention that measure the decision and choice factors.

Evenues for Future Research

As this study elaborates several factors which effect the student's choice to choose a specific business school. These factors include the location of campus, HEC ranking, qualification of faculty, and fee structure etc. this study provides condusive grounds for future research in dealing with the each aspect seperately mentioned above. It can be further extended in terms of adressing the each business school and student's inclination towards it. Hence, this reseach provides a base for future research.

Conclusions

Aim of this research paper is enhance the knowledge of students and parents and provides brief information while selecting a particular business school where their financial and educational resources can be worthwhile. All the necessary data gathered and analyzed provides information, recommendations and implementations for all the business schools in Pakistan to improve their policies and practices to attract more students.

It is also useful research for Higher Education Commission of Pakistan to make policies in such way which are in students favor and student attract towards them. Also they can easily find out the key success factors of quality education by this study so they can ensure that parameters when assigning ranks to the universities as well as when taking important decisions.

Purpose of this study is to address the problem of students and their parents while selecting a business school for higher studies. This research work provide complete understanding to those factors which may or may not have influence on decisions of students and their parents while selecting a particular business school. In Pakistan, students and their families faces too many problems while selecting a business school so this study gives a complete package of information to them for decision making process.

This research work is most important influence the knowledge and addresses the literature gap and provides strong insight information to the future studies on the topic of student's choice in Pakistan and factors affecting their choices while selecting a business school.

References

1. Bashir, R., Hassan, A., Pasha, M. A., & Ahmed, S. (2013). Analysis of Internal & External Factors Affecting Choice of Business Schools by Students. *Journal of Management and Social Sciences*, 9(2), 31-41.

2. Abdullah, A. M., &Saeid, M. (2016). Factors Affecting Students' Choice for MBA Program in Kuwait Universities. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 11(3), 119.
3. Joseph, F. B. (2013). Factors influencing the selection of business studies: a comparative study of Indian students at an Indian University and Chinese students at a Thai university. *AU-GSB e-JOURNAL*, 6(1).
4. Jain, D., &Shrimali, M. (2013). SOURCES OF INFORMATION INFLUENCING STUDENTS'SELECTION OF B-SCHOOLS. *Researchers World*, 4(3), 101.
5. Jain, D., &Shrimali, M. (2013). SOURCES OF INFORMATION INFLUENCING STUDENTS'SELECTION OF B-SCHOOLS. *Researchers World*, 4(3), 101.
6. Chantasuwanno, S., &Suasungnern, S. (2011). The motivation and satisfaction of students towards MBA at Karlstad University.
7. Waseem, S. N., &Zarif, T. (2012). Factors affecting students' choice for degree in business administration. *Journal of management and social sciences*, 8(1), 40-47.
8. Chapman, D. (1981), "A model of student college choice," *Journal of Higher Education*, 52(5), pp. 490-505
9. Carpenter, P.G. & Fleishman, J.A.(1987), "Linking intentions and behavior: Australian students' college plans and college attendance," *American Educational Research Journal*, 24(1), pp. 70-105
10. Manski, C. & Wise, D.(1983), "College Choice in America" Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press
11. Hossler, D. (1984). "Enrollment management: An integrated approach," New York, College Entrance Examination Board
12. Hossler, D., Bean, J. P. & Associates, (1990) "The strategic management of college enrollments" San Francisco, Jossey-Bass, Inc.
13. Hossler, D. & Gallagher, K. (1987), "Studying student college choice: A three-phase model and the implications for policy makers," *Collegeand University*. 62(3), pp. 207-221.
14. Servicer, R. A. (1986) "freshmen at competitive liberal arts college: A survey of factors influencing institutional choice" Unpublished dissertation, Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio.
15. Sevier, R. A., (1992) "Recruiting African-American undergraduates: A national survey of the factors that affect intuitional choice," *College and University*, 68, pp. 48-51.
16. Servicer, R. A. (1994), "Image is everything: Strategies for measuring, changing and maintaining your institution's image," (White paper No.1) Cedar Rapids, IA: Stamats Communications, Inc.
17. Sevier, R. A. (1998), "Charting a course: Finding direction amidst the swell of data on student recruiting," White Paper No. 6, Cedar Rapids, IA, Stamats Communication, Inc.